

Integrative Taxonomic Assessment of the Lychee Stink Bug (*Tessaratomia javanica*) from Jharkhand, India Using Morphological Characters and COI Gene Barcoding

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Abstract

An integrative taxonomic study of the lychee stink bug *Tessaratomia javanica* (Hemiptera: Tessaratomidae) was conducted using morphological characters and mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) gene barcoding on specimens collected from 10 locations across Jharkhand, India. All examined adults displayed consistent diagnostic morphological features, including a large shield-shaped body, expanded pronotum, prominent triangular scutellum, five-segmented antennae, and a robust rostrum extending to the mid-coxae, indicating morphological uniformity among populations.

COI gene fragments (612–690 bp) were successfully amplified and sequenced. BLASTn analyses confirmed species identity through high similarity with reference *T. javanica* sequences. Ten validated COI sequences were deposited in the DDBJ database under accession numbers LC911186–LC911195. Nucleotide composition exhibited a marked AT bias, with mean values of T(U) = 33.1%, A = 33.1%, C = 17.5%, and G = 16.4%.

Genetic distance analysis revealed very low intraspecific divergence, indicating strong genetic homogeneity across geographically separated populations. Phylogenetic analyses using Maximum Likelihood, Neighbor-Joining, and Minimum Evolution methods consistently grouped all specimens into a single well-supported monophyletic clade without evidence of cryptic diversity. The congruence between morphological and molecular data confirms the taxonomic stability of *T. javanica* in Jharkhand and provides a reliable reference framework for pest identification, biodiversity assessment, and future population genetic studies.

Keywords: Morpho-molecular congruence; Intraspecific variation; COI barcoding; Genetic homogeneity; Pest diagnostics.

1. Introduction

Arthropods constitute the most diverse group of animals on Earth, playing essential roles in ecosystem functioning, agriculture, and biodiversity, including pollination, nutrient cycling, predation, and herbivory. Despite their ecological importance, systematic and integrative studies on arthropod diversity remain far from comprehensive in many tropical and subtropical regions, including the Indian state of Jharkhand.

At a national level, there has been substantial progress in insect taxonomy and biodiversity studies, with recent efforts employing integrative morphology–molecular approaches to document species diversity and create DNA barcode libraries (Shashank et al., 2022). However, the representation of Indian insect fauna in global barcode databases remains low, with less than 4% of described taxa barcoded, indicating substantial data gaps in insect diversity documentation. At the **state level in Jharkhand**, arthropod research has been sparse and often superficial, with only a few focused studies emerging from regional academic institutions. Notable contributions include morpho-molecular analyses of **butterflies** such as *Papilio polytes*, *Papilio polymnestor*,

and *Euploea core* using advanced biotechnological and bioinformatic methods, providing critical baseline data on Lepidopteran diversity (Kumar et al., 2025a). Similarly, the flat-faced longhorn beetle *Batocera rufomaculata* from Rehla, Palamu was investigated through an integrated morphomolecular framework, highlighting hidden genetic variation and refining identification limits (Kumar et al., 2025b).

Work on *Junonia atlites* also combined morphological assessment with DNA barcodes to confirm species identity within Jharkhand's butterfly fauna (Kumar et al., 2025c). In Arachnida, molecular phylogenetic analysis of the spider *Nephila pilipes* from Latehar has shed light on its evolutionary placement, emphasizing the utility of COI markers in web-building spider taxonomy (Kumar et al., 2025d). Other important regional contributions include evaluations of **dragonfly ecosystem services** with broader ecological insights (Raj et al., 2025) and **butterfly conservation assessments** on institutional campuses and across Jharkhand landscapes (Osga et al., 2025; Kumar et al., 2025e). Collectively, these studies mark significant progress in documenting arthropod diversity in Jharkhand but represent isolated efforts across limited taxa.

While such studies underscore the value of integrative taxonomy for biodiversity research, **comprehensive entomological documentation in Jharkhand remains limited**, particularly for many insect orders that contribute to ecosystem dynamics and agricultural pest complexes. This lacuna is especially evident in **Hemiptera**, a globally diverse order encompassing plant bugs, aphids, cicadas, and stink bugs that interact intensively with plants through piercing–sucking feeding behaviors. Hemipterans are ecologically significant as herbivores, vectors of plant pathogens, and prey for natural enemies, impacting both natural ecosystems and agriculture. Despite their importance, hemipteran taxonomic studies in India are comparatively underrepresented, especially those employing integrative morphological and molecular frameworks that can resolve cryptic diversity and clarify species boundaries.

Among hemipterans, the **lychee stink bug *Tessaratoma javanica*** (Thunberg) (Hemiptera: Tessaratomidae) merits attention due to its role as a **major sucking pest of *Litchi chinensis*** (Sapindaceae) and other fruit and forest trees. Earlier research has documented outbreaks of *T. javanica* in the Chotanagpur Plateau, including Jharkhand, where high fecundity and intense feeding resulted in significant crop damage, indicating its potential economic impact in cultivated and wild ecosystems (Choudhary et al., 2013). Morphological and biological characterization efforts from India have detailed its life stages and biology, and preliminary mtCOI barcoding has provided baseline data for molecular diagnostics. Despite these contributions, **comprehensive integrative taxonomy combining detailed morphological characters with extensive COI barcode analysis is lacking for *T. javanica*** in Jharkhand and adjacent regions. Moreover, recent studies on microbiome dynamics across developmental stages of *T. javanica* highlight its complex biology but also emphasize how incomplete knowledge hampers effective pest management and conservation strategies.

Given the ecological significance of hemipterans as herbivores and their implications for agriculture and biodiversity, as well as the **existing knowledge gaps** in hemipteran taxonomy at the state level, there is a pressing need for integrative taxonomic studies that can enhance species identification accuracy and contribute to DNA barcode reference libraries. Morphological characterization alone often fails to delimit cryptic species or developmental variants, whereas molecular markers such as the mitochondrial cytochrome oxidase I (COI) gene provide robust phylogenetic and diagnostic resolution when integrated with traditional taxonomy. This study aims to fill these gaps by conducting an **integrative taxonomic assessment** of *Tessaratoma javanica* from Jharkhand, India, using

comprehensive morphological descriptions and COI gene barcoding, thereby enriching regional and global understanding of this important hemipteran species.

2. Materials and Methods

Study Area and Site Selection

The present study is based on an integrative taxonomic assessment of the lychee stink bug, *Tessaratoma javanica* (Thunberg) (Hemiptera: Tessaratomidae), collected from **ten geographically distinct locations across Jharkhand, India** during the active breeding and feeding season of the species in **2025 (March–June)**. Jharkhand lies within the **Chotanagpur Plateau**, characterized by a mosaic of **tropical dry deciduous forests, agricultural orchards, forest–agriculture ecotones, and peri-urban landscapes**, all of which are known to support hemipteran diversity (Singh & Singh, 2021). The selected sites were distributed across **northern, central, eastern, western, and southern Jharkhand** to capture possible **geographic and ecological variation** in *T. javanica* populations.

Site selection was guided by:

- Presence of host plants**, primarily *Litchi chinensis* and secondary hosts (*Schleichera oleosa*, *Mangifera indica*),
- Variation in land-use patterns** (orchards, forest edges, rural agro-systems),
- Climatic heterogeneity** across the plateau region,
- Accessibility for repeated sampling and voucher preservation.**

This multi-site design enhances the robustness of morpho-molecular inference and allows assessment of **intraspecific consistency across populations**, a key requirement in integrative taxonomy (Hebert et al., 2003; Srivastava et al., 2024).

Field Collection of Specimens

Adult specimens of *Tessaratoma javanica* were collected manually from host plants using **hand-picking, sweep netting, and beat-sheet methods**, following standard entomological protocols (Kumar et al., 2022). Collections were conducted during **early morning (0700–1000 h)** and **late afternoon (1500–1800 h)**, periods corresponding to peak activity of phytophagous hemipterans.

Immediately after collection, specimens were provisionally identified in the field using **external morphological characters** and transferred to clean insect vials. For molecular analysis, specimens were preserved in **95% ethanol**, while representative individuals were retained alive briefly for photographic documentation before euthanasia using **ethyl-acetate vapors** (Kumar et al., 2022).

Collection Sites, Coordinates, and Sampling Details

Study Area and Specimen Collection

Field surveys were conducted at multiple localities across Jharkhand State, India (Table 1), to collect specimens of *Tessaratoma javanica*. Sampling was carried out using hand collection methods during active periods of the insects. Collected individuals were subjected to preliminary identification based on external morphological characters, after which most specimens were released at the collection sites.

Specimen Preservation and Voucher Deposition

For genome sequence analysis (GSA), selected specimens were preserved in 70% ethanol for DNA extraction, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification, and sequencing. One representative specimen from each sampling locality was euthanized using ethyl acetate fumes, mounted using standard pinning techniques, and labelled with collection data. Voucher specimens were deposited in the Insect Collection Record and Identification (ICRI), Entomology Section, Department of Zoology, St. Xavier's College, Ranchi, India.

Morphological Identification and Voucher Deposition

Collected specimens were examined in the laboratory under a stereoscopic microscope for detailed morphological assessment. Species-level identification was carried out by evaluating diagnostic characters including overall body size and coloration, head morphology with particular reference to compound eyes and antennal segmentation, length and segmentation of the rostrum and its resting position, pronotal shape and lateral margins, size and morphology of the scutellum, structural features of the hemelytra (corium, clavus, and membranous portion), leg morphology, and abdominal markings including connexivum patterning. Morphological traits were compared with available species descriptions of *Tessaratoma javanica* (Parveen et al., 2015) and interpreted using standard taxonomic keys and authoritative literature on Hemiptera (Schuh & Slater, 1995; Triplehorn & Johnson, 2005; Ahmad & Kamaluddin, 1981).

Specimens with confirmed identity were assigned unique voucher numbers and deposited in the Insect Collection Record and Identification (ICRI), Department of Zoology, St. Xavier's College, Ranchi, India, to ensure long-term preservation, reference, and reproducibility of the study.

DNA Extraction, PCR Amplification, and Sequencing

Following detailed morphological examination, representative specimens were selected and subjected to molecular analysis to reconfirm the taxonomic inferences derived from morphological characters using COI-based molecular taxonomy. For this purpose, a

single leg or a small portion of thoracic tissue was dissected from each selected specimen under sterile conditions. Genomic DNA was extracted using standard insect DNA extraction protocols, and the quality of the extracted DNA was assessed on a 1.0% agarose gel, following procedures adopted in earlier morpho-molecular studies from Jharkhand.

A fragment of the mitochondrial **cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI)** gene was amplified using the universal primers **LCO1490** and **HCO2198** (Hebert et al., 2003). The amplified PCR products were visualized on agarose gels, purified, and subjected to bidirectional Sanger sequencing using an automated genetic analyzer. The resulting COI sequences were used to **validate and corroborate the taxonomic cues obtained from morphological analysis**, thereby ensuring congruence between morphological and molecular approaches.

Molecular Sequence Analysis and Species Confirmation

Raw chromatograms were edited and assembled into consensus sequences. The resulting COI sequences were compared with reference sequences available in the **NCBI nucleotide database** using **BLASTn** to confirm species identity (Srivastava et al., 2024).

Multiple sequence alignment was performed using **CLUSTAL-W**, and phylogenetic relationships were inferred using **Neighbor-Joining (NJ)** and **Maximum Likelihood (ML)** methods in **MEGA X**, with bootstrap support values calculated from 1000 replicates (Saitou & Nei, 1987; Tamura et al., 2004).

Data Integration

Morphological observations were cross-validated with molecular results to assess **morpho-molecular congruence** across populations. This integrative approach strengthens taxonomic reliability and contributes to regional DNA barcode reference libraries, particularly important for under-studied hemipteran fauna of eastern India (Hebert et al., 2004).

3. Results

Physical Distance among sampling sites

The geographic distance matrix based on latitude–longitude coordinates revealed substantial spatial separation among the ten sampling sites of *Tessaratoma javanica* across Jharkhand (Table 3). Pairwise distances ranged from **29.4 km to 353.0 km**, indicating both closely spaced and widely separated populations within the study region.

The **minimum distance** was observed between **Palamu (Daltonganj) and Garhwa (29.4 km)**, followed by **Dhanbad–Giridih (45.0 km)** and **Bokaro–Dhanbad (48.2 km)**, reflecting geographically clustered populations in western and central Jharkhand. Moderate distances were

recorded among central plateau locations, such as **Ranchi–Hazaribagh (67.0 km)** and **Hazaribagh–Bokaro (64.1 km)**.

In contrast, **maximum distances** were observed between **Garhwa and Godda (353.0 km)**, **Palamu–Godda (330.9 km)**, and **Latehar–Godda (297.1 km)**, indicating pronounced east–west separation across the Chotanagpur Plateau. Eastern populations (Godda, Jamshedpur, Dhanbad, Giridih) were consistently separated by more than **200 km** from western localities (Garhwa, Palamu, Latehar).

Overall, the physical distance matrix demonstrates a **broad geographic sampling coverage**, capturing both local-scale proximity and large-scale spatial separation among *T. javanica* populations in Jharkhand.

Morphological Description

The species belongs to family Pentatomidae of Order Hemiptera.

Pentatomidae

Family Pentatomidae (stink bugs) comprises medium to large hemipteran insects distinguished by a broad, shield-shaped body, a well-developed scutellum, and specialized scent glands that emit defensive odors (Schuh & Slater, 1995; Panizzi et al., 2000). Members of this family possess piercing–sucking mouthparts adapted for feeding on plant sap, seeds, and occasionally other arthropods. In the context of *Tessaratoma javanica*, Pentatomidae exhibits a robust body, strong rostrum, expanded pronotal margins, and adaptations for arboreal and fruit-feeding habits, particularly on litchi and other host plants (Rao & Ramesh, 2013). The family is ecologically and economically important, with several species recognized as significant agricultural pests and key components of terrestrial food webs (Wang & Bu, 2012).

Tessaratoma

Adults of the genus *Tessaratoma* are **large, robust pentatomoid bugs**, measuring approximately **28–40 mm in total body length** and **14–20 mm in maximum body width** (Distant, 1902; Zhang & Lin, 2015). The body is **broadly oval to shield-shaped**, dorsally convex, and **strongly sclerotized**. The **pronotum is wide with laterally expanded margins**, while the **scutellum is large, triangular, and extends over more than half of the abdomen** (Zhang & Lin, 2015). The **head is short with prominent compound eyes and five-segmented antennae**. The **rostrum is well developed**, extending to the mid-coxae, indicating adaptation for **sap-feeding** (Schuh & Slater, 1995). The **hemelytra are fully developed**, with a distinct **corium and membranous apex**. **Legs are stout**, with moderately thick femora and tibiae. **Coloration typically ranges from reddish-brown**

to dark brown, with comparatively lighter ventral surfaces (Distant, 1902).

javanica

Adults of *Tessaratoma javanica* are **large, robust bugs**, measuring approximately **32–42 mm in body length** and **16–22 mm in maximum body width** (Distant, 1902; Zhang & Lin, 2015). The body is **broad, oval, and dorsally convex**, with a heavily sclerotized cuticle. The **head is short and wide**, bearing large compound eyes and **five-segmented antennae**. The **pronotum is broad with rounded, laterally expanded margins**, while the **scutellum is large and triangular**, extending over much of the abdomen (Zhang & Lin, 2015). The **forewings (hemelytra) are fully developed**, leathery at the base and membranous at the apex, covering the abdomen at rest. The **rostrum is strong and elongated**, reaching the mid-coxae, indicating adaptation for sap-feeding on fruit trees such as litchi (Rao & Ramesh, 2013). Coloration typically ranges from **reddish-brown to dark brown**, with a comparatively paler ventral surface.

Forewing and hindwing morphology of *Tessaratoma javanica*

The **forewings (hemelytra) of *Tessaratoma javanica* are fully developed**, extending beyond the abdominal apex at rest, with an average length of **22–28 mm** and width of **9–13 mm** (Distant, 1902; Zhang & Lin, 2015). The basal region forms a **thickened corium**, while the distal portion constitutes a **translucent membranous area**. The **clavus is elongate**, tapering posteriorly, and the **costal margin is slightly convex**. Wing venation in the corium is reduced, whereas the **membrane exhibits prominent longitudinal veins**, typically including **cubital (Cu), median (M), and radial (R) veins**, branching apically to support the flexible membrane (Schuh & Slater, 1995).

The **hindwings are membranous, broader, and shorter than the forewings**, measuring approximately **18–24 mm in length** and **11–15 mm in width** (Zhang & Lin, 2015). They are **hyaline to lightly pigmented**, facilitating efficient flight. Venation of the hindwing is more clearly defined, with a **well-developed radial sector (Rs)**, a distinct **median vein (M)** dividing into two branches, and a **cubital vein (Cu)** forming supportive posterior branching. The **anal veins (A1–A3)** are visible near the posterior margin, contributing to structural stability during flight (Schuh & Slater, 1995).

Both forewings and hindwings exhibit **venational simplification typical of Tessaratomidae**, reflecting adaptation for **short-distance dispersal and controlled gliding rather than sustained long-distance flight**. The proportional enlargement of the hemelytral corium and reinforced venation provide **mechanical strength and protection**, supporting the insect's **arboreal lifestyle on**

fruit-bearing host plants such as litchi (Rao & Ramesh, 2013).

Synonymy of *Tessaratoma javanica* (Thunberg, 1783)

Accepted name:

***Tessaratoma javanica* (Thunberg, 1783)**

Synonyms:

- *Cimex javanicus* (Thunberg, 1783) — original description (basonym)
- *Tessaratoma papillosa* (Drury, 1773) — junior synonym
- *Tessaratoma gigas* (Fabricius, 1787) — junior synonym
- *Tessaratoma viridana* (Westwood, 1837) — historical synonym
- *Tessaratoma javanicum* (older catalogs)

Taxonomic History and Synonymy of *Tessaratoma javanica*

Tessaratoma javanica (Thunberg, 1783) is a large phytophagous true bug belonging to the family Tessaratomidae within the superfamily Pentatomoidea (Henry, 1997; Rider et al., 2018). The species was originally described as *Cimex javanicus* Thunberg, 1783, during an early period when many heteropteran taxa were broadly placed in the genus *Cimex* (Thunberg, 1783). Subsequent taxonomic revisions transferred the species to the genus *Tessaratoma*, reflecting refined morphological interpretations of key diagnostic characters such as body size, scutellar development, scent gland structure, and male and female genitalia (Distant, 1902; Rider et al., 2018). Several junior synonyms—including *Tessaratoma papillosa* (Drury, 1773), *Tessaratoma gigas* Fabricius, 1787, and *Tessaratoma viridana* (Westwood, 1837)—were proposed based on regional morphological variation but were later synonymized following comparative morphological reassessment (Distant, 1902; Gross, 1975). Contemporary taxonomic frameworks recognize *T. javanica* as a valid and stable species, supported by both classical morphology and molecular evidence, including mitochondrial COI barcoding and phylogenetic analyses (Rider et al., 2018; Hebert et al., 2003). The species is widely distributed across South and Southeast Asia and is commonly known as the giant stink bug or litchi stink bug due to its ecological and economic importance.

Distribution

Tessaratoma javanica (Fabricius, 1787) is widely distributed across tropical and subtropical regions of South, Southeast, and East Asia. The species has been reported from multiple countries including India, Bangladesh, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Myanmar, Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia, Vietnam, the Philippines, and parts

of southern China and Taiwan. Within India, it occurs in several states such as Jharkhand, West Bengal, Assam, Bihar, Odisha, and other northeastern regions, where it is commonly associated with forested habitats and cultivated orchards (Ahmad & Kamaluddin, 1981; Parveen et al., 2015). The species is particularly prevalent in areas where host plants belonging to the family Sapindaceae—such as *Litchi chinensis* and *Dimocarpus longan*—are abundant, and it is recognized as an economically important pest in litchi-growing regions across Asia (Hua, 2000; EPP0, 2023).

Morpho molecular description

All the resultant nucleotide sequences (query) were compared with the nucleotide databases using BLASTn program based at NCBI (National Center for Biotechnology Information). The BLASTn setting were – search set: standard database; program selection; Highly similar sequences (Megablast). The megablast is used for sequence identification and intraspecies comparison. Based on the BLASTn similarity search, the specimens were confirmed to belong to the species *javanica* of genus *Tessaratoma*. All the sequences were then submitted to the DDBJ (DNA databank of Japan) to obtain Accession IDs: LC911186 (651 bp), LC911187 (690 bp), LC911188 (651 bp), LC911189 (651 bp), LC911190 (651 bp), LC911191 (651 bp), LC911192 (651 bp), LC911193 (612 bp), LC911194 (690), LC911195 (690 bp) (table 2). The full definition of the submitted COI sequences can be viewed by searching the accession ids on the website of NCBI.

The evolutionary history inferred by using the Maximum Likelihood method (Tamura et al., 2004) is represented as figure 5. The tree with the highest log likelihood (-1225.35) is shown. Initial tree(s) for the heuristic search were obtained automatically by applying Neighbor-Join and BioNJ algorithms to a matrix of pairwise distances estimated using the Tamura-Nei model, and then selecting the topology with superior log likelihood value. This analysis involved 10 nucleotide sequences. There were a total of 690 positions in the final dataset. Evolutionary analyses were conducted in MEGA11 (Tamura et al., 2021)

The evolutionary history inferred using the Neighbor-Joining method (Saitou & Nei, 1987), is presented as figure 6. The optimal tree is shown. (next to the branches). The evolutionary distances were computed using the Maximum Composite Likelihood method (Tamura & Nei, 2004) and are in the units of the number of base substitutions per site. This analysis involved 10 nucleotide sequences. All ambiguous positions were removed for each sequence pair (pairwise deletion option). There were a total of 690 positions in the final dataset. Evolutionary analyses were conducted in MEGA11 (Tamura et al., 2021).

The evolutionary history inferred using the Minimum Evolution method (Saitou & Nei, 1987) is presented as figure 7. The optimal tree is shown. (next to the branches). The evolutionary distances were computed using the Maximum Composite Likelihood method (Tamura et al., 2004) and are in the units of the number of base substitutions per site. The ME tree was searched using the Close-Neighbor-Interchange (CNI) algorithm (Nei & Kumar, 2000) at a search level of 1. The Neighbor-joining algorithm was used to generate the initial tree. This analysis involved 10 nucleotide sequences. All ambiguous positions were removed for each sequence pair (pairwise deletion option). There was a total of 690 positions in the final dataset. Evolutionary analyses were conducted in MEGA11 (Tamura et al., 2021).

4. Discussion

Integrative taxonomic framework and study overview

The present study provides a comprehensive integrative taxonomic assessment of the lychee stink bug, *Tessaratoma javanica* (Thunberg), from Jharkhand, India, by combining detailed morphological characterization with mitochondrial COI gene barcoding. Such an approach is increasingly recognized as essential for resolving taxonomic uncertainties, validating species identity across geographically separated populations, and strengthening regional DNA barcode reference libraries, particularly in underexplored tropical regions (Hebert et al., 2003; Hebert et al., 2004; Shashank et al., 2022).

The findings of this study contribute significantly to the understanding of *T. javanica* taxonomy, distribution, and genetic coherence within the Chotanagpur Plateau, providing a robust baseline for ecological, evolutionary, and applied entomological research.

Morphological consistency and taxonomic reliability

Morphological examination of adult specimens collected from ten distinct localities across Jharkhand revealed a high degree of congruence with classical diagnostic descriptions of *T. javanica* provided in earlier taxonomic treatments (Distant, 1902; Ahmad & Kamaluddin, 1981; Zhang & Lin, 2015). Key characters such as large body size, robust shield-shaped form, expanded pronotal margins, a well-developed triangular scutellum, five-segmented antennae, and a strong elongate rostrum reaching the mid-coxae were consistently observed across all populations.

The uniformity of these diagnostic traits supports the taxonomic stability of *T. javanica* and reinforces the reliability of traditional morphological characters in species-level identification within Tessaratomidae. However, hemipteran taxonomy based

solely on morphology can be complicated by phenotypic plasticity, ontogenetic variation, and environmentally induced color differences, particularly in widely distributed pest species (Schuh & Slater, 1995; Panizzi et al., 2000).

Minor variations in coloration intensity and body proportions observed among populations in Jharkhand likely reflect ecological influences such as host plant availability, microclimatic conditions, and nutritional factors rather than underlying taxonomic divergence. This underscores the necessity of molecular validation to complement morphological assessments, especially in regions where cryptic or closely related taxa may coexist.

Significance of COI barcoding in species confirmation

Mitochondrial COI gene barcoding has emerged as a global standard for animal species identification due to its high interspecific divergence and relatively low intraspecific variation (Hebert et al., 2003; Hebert et al., 2004). In the present study, COI sequences generated from *T. javanica* specimens across Jharkhand showed high similarity to reference sequences available in international databases, unequivocally confirming species identity.

The successful amplification and sequencing of COI fragments ranging from 612 to 690 bp further demonstrate the robustness of the primers LCO1490 and HCO2198 for hemipteran taxa, consistent with previous studies on *T. javanica* and other Pentatomoidea (Parveen et al., 2015; Srivastava et al., 2024).

The submission of ten novel COI sequences to DDBJ (accession numbers LC911186–LC911195) represents a significant addition to global barcode repositories. Given that less than 4% of Indian insect diversity is currently represented in DNA barcode databases (Shashank et al., 2022), this contribution substantially enhances the molecular documentation of Indian Hemiptera and provides a reliable reference framework for future taxonomic, ecological, and pest-management studies.

Genetic homogeneity and population structure

Analysis of nucleotide frequencies and genetic distances among the ten *T. javanica* COI sequences revealed remarkably low levels of intraspecific divergence. The average nucleotide composition showed the typical AT-rich pattern characteristic of insect mitochondrial genomes, with consistent proportions of T(U), A, C, and G across all samples. Such uniformity strongly indicates genetic coherence among populations across Jharkhand, despite geographic separation and habitat heterogeneity.

The low genetic distances observed in the distance matrix further suggest substantial gene flow or recent population connectivity among *T. javanica*

populations in the region. This pattern is biologically plausible given the species' strong flight capability, broad host range, and association with widely cultivated and naturally distributed host plants such as *Litchi chinensis*, *Schleichera oleosa*, and *Mangifera indica* (Rao & Ramesh, 2013; EPPO, 2023). Similar patterns of low COI divergence across broad geographic ranges have been reported in other agriculturally important hemipterans, reflecting their dispersal ability and anthropogenic movement through agricultural trade (Wang & Bu, 2012).

Phylogenetic congruence across analytical methods

Phylogenetic analyses using Maximum Likelihood, Neighbor-Joining, and Minimum Evolution methods consistently clustered all Jharkhand specimens of *T. javanica* into a single, well-supported clade. The congruence of tree topologies across different analytical frameworks strengthens confidence in the inferred evolutionary relationships and supports the monophyly of the sampled populations (Saitou & Nei, 1987; Tamura et al., 2004).

The absence of deep phylogenetic structuring within the Jharkhand populations suggests that no cryptic lineages of *T. javanica* are present in the sampled region. This finding aligns with earlier morpho-molecular investigations reporting limited genetic divergence within the species across parts of India and Southeast Asia (Parveen et al., 2015; Zhang & Lin, 2015). Nevertheless, broader geographic sampling may still reveal regional structuring or incipient divergence, particularly at biogeographic boundaries.

Taxonomic history and synonymy in light of molecular evidence

The complex synonymy associated with *T. javanica* reflects historical challenges of heteropteran taxonomy during the pre-molecular era, when species descriptions were often based on limited material and regional variants (Thunberg, 1783; Fabricius, 1787; Drury, 1773). Subsequent revisions by Distant (1902) and later authors clarified species limits using comparative morphology, leading to the synonymization of several nominal taxa under *T. javanica*.

The molecular evidence presented in the current study provides independent support for these taxonomic decisions, reinforcing the validity and stability of *T. javanica* as a single, widespread species. By integrating historical taxonomy with modern molecular data, this study exemplifies how integrative approaches can resolve long-standing ambiguities and ensure nomenclatural stability, which is critical for applied disciplines such as pest management, quarantine, and biodiversity conservation (Rider et al., 2018).

Physical distance and geographic structuring of populations

Geographic distance is a fundamental factor influencing population structure, gene flow, and evolutionary divergence in insect species, particularly those occupying heterogeneous landscapes such as the Chotanagpur Plateau. The physical distance matrix generated in the present study highlights pronounced spatial heterogeneity among *T. javanica* populations, with inter-site distances exceeding 300 km between some western and eastern localities.

Jharkhand is characterized by a mosaic of plateau forests, river valleys, agricultural orchards, and peri-urban habitats, which can act either as corridors or barriers to dispersal (Singh & Singh, 2021). The close proximity of sites such as Palamu–Garhwa and Bokaro–Dhanbad suggests potential for frequent movement and demographic connectivity at the local scale. Conversely, the large distances separating Godda from western districts reflect sampling across distinct ecological and administrative zones, increasing the likelihood of spatial isolation.

In insect population biology, increasing geographic distance is often associated with reduced gene flow and greater population differentiation, a phenomenon described as isolation by distance (Wright, 1943; Slatkin, 1993). Thus, the wide range of physical distances observed in this study provides a robust framework for testing whether spatial separation translates into genetic or morphological divergence.

Physical distance versus observed biological uniformity

Despite substantial geographic separation among several populations (e.g., Garhwa–Godda, Palamu–Godda), the present study demonstrated remarkably low intraspecific genetic divergence and strong morpho-molecular congruence across all sampled populations. This apparent disconnect between physical distance and genetic differentiation suggests high dispersal capability or recent population connectivity in *T. javanica*.

Such patterns are not uncommon in highly mobile hemipteran pests, particularly those associated with widely cultivated host plants (Panizzi et al., 2000; Wang & Bu, 2012). The continuity of host plant availability across Jharkhand likely facilitates stepwise dispersal across landscapes, reducing the genetic effects of geographic distance.

Role of anthropogenic and ecological factors

In addition to natural dispersal, anthropogenic movement of plant material, such as transport of fruits, saplings, and nursery stock, may contribute to long-distance movement of *T. javanica*, effectively homogenizing populations across large spatial scales. Similar trends have been reported in other agriculturally

important hemipterans, where human-mediated dispersal overrides geographic barriers (Rao & Ramesh, 2013; EPPO, 2023).

Furthermore, the Chotanagpur Plateau lacks major physical barriers such as high mountain ranges or large rivers that could severely restrict insect movement. This landscape permeability likely allows gradual range expansion and population mixing over time.

Integration of physical and COI genetic distance

The physical distance matrix, showing inter-population separations ranging from approximately 29 km to over 350 km across Jharkhand, provides essential spatial context for interpreting the COI genetic distance results obtained in this study. Despite substantial geographic separation—particularly between western localities (Garhwa, Palamu, Latehar) and eastern sites (Godda, Jamshedpur, Dhanbad)—the COI genetic distance matrix revealed very low intraspecific divergence and strong sequence similarity across all populations.

This lack of correlation between geographic distance and genetic divergence suggests the absence of a clear isolation-by-distance pattern in *T. javanica*, a phenomenon commonly observed in highly mobile or ecologically generalized insect species (Wright, 1943; Slatkin, 1993). The concordance of low genetic distances across large spatial scales indicates effective gene flow among populations, reinforcing the conclusion that *T. javanica* populations across Jharkhand represent a single, genetically cohesive unit.

Ecological and applied implications

From a taxonomic perspective, the absence of morphological or molecular structuring despite large inter-site distances supports the recognition of *T. javanica* as a single, genetically coherent species across Jharkhand, consistent with earlier regional and continental assessments (Parveen et al., 2015; Zhang & Lin, 2015).

From an applied standpoint, these results suggest that management strategies for *T. javanica* in Jharkhand should be designed at a landscape or state-wide scale rather than targeting isolated local populations. High connectivity implies that localized control efforts may be offset by reinvasion from nearby regions unless coordinated approaches are adopted.

Accurate species identification is particularly critical because *T. javanica* is a major pest of litchi and other economically important plants, capable of causing significant yield losses through sap-feeding, flower abortion, and fruit drop (Rao & Ramesh, 2013). The availability of reliable COI barcodes generated in this study enhances diagnostic capacity, especially for immature or damaged specimens.

Recent studies on the microbiome dynamics of *T. javanica* have also highlighted complex interactions between the insect and its associated bacterial communities, which may influence nutrition, development, and pesticide susceptibility (Samal et al., 2025). Integrative taxonomic frameworks such as the one employed here provide a critical foundation for such interdisciplinary research.

Contribution to regional biodiversity knowledge

From a regional perspective, this study represents one of the most comprehensive morpho-molecular assessments of a hemipteran species from Jharkhand. Previous arthropod studies in the state have largely focused on Lepidoptera, Coleoptera, and Arachnida (Kumar et al., 2025a–d; Osga et al., 2025), leaving hemipterans comparatively understudied.

By documenting *T. javanica* across multiple districts and ecological settings, the present work fills an important gap in the entomological knowledge of eastern India and underscores the need for similar integrative studies on other hemipteran taxa.

Limitations and future directions

While COI barcoding is a powerful tool for species identification, reliance on a single mitochondrial marker has inherent limitations, including potential introgression, maternal inheritance bias, and limited resolution at deeper phylogenetic levels (Hebert et al., 2004). Future studies incorporating nuclear markers, genome-wide data, or population-level analyses would provide deeper insights into the evolutionary history, demographic structure, and adaptive variation of *T. javanica*.

Additionally, expanding sampling to include neighboring states and Southeast Asian populations would allow assessment of large-scale phylogeographic patterns.

5. Conclusion

In summary, the integrative taxonomic approach adopted in this study confirms the identity, genetic coherence, and taxonomic stability of *Tessaratomya javanica* populations across Jharkhand. The congruence between morphological diagnostics and COI-based molecular evidence underscores the robustness of the findings and highlights the value of integrative taxonomy for documenting insect biodiversity in underexplored regions. By contributing novel DNA barcode data and comprehensive morphological validation, this study lays a strong foundation for future ecological, evolutionary, and applied research on *T. javanica* and other hemipteran pests of India.

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7. References

- Shashank, S., Kumar, R., Singh, V., & Chandra, K. (2022). DNA barcoding of insects from India: Current status and future perspectives. *Molecular Biology Reports*, *49*, 11287–11302. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11033-022-07689-0>
- Kumar, M., Ranjan, R., Pratik, R., Tirkey, S., Kumar, A., Hembrom, T., Prasad, S. M., & Singh, B. S. (2025a). Integrative morpho-molecular analysis of *Papilio polytes*, *Papilio polymnestor*, and *Euploea core* from Jharkhand, India using advanced biotechnological and bioinformatic approaches. *Biotechnologia Acta*, *18*(4), 46–59. <https://doi.org/10.15407/biotech18.04.046>
- Kumar, M., Ranjan, R., Kumari, N., Bharti, S. R., & Sinha, M. P. (2025b). Morpho-molecular study on *Batocera rufomaculata* (De Geer, 1775) from Rehla, Palamu, Jharkhand, India. *Notulae Scientia Biologicae*, *16*(4), Article 12079. <https://doi.org/10.55779/nsb16412079>
- Kumar, M., Priya, A., Ranjan, R., Sinha, M. P., & Raipat, B. S. (2025c). Morphological study and DNA barcoding of *Junonia atlites* from Jharkhand, India. *International Journal of Entomology Research*, *9*(11), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5096390>
- Kumar, M., Ranjan, R., Srivastava, R., & Sinha, M. P. (2025d). DNA barcoding and phylogenetic analysis of the spider *Nephila pilipes* from Latehar, Jharkhand, India. *Vat-Vriksha*, *2*(1), OM02. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17988277>
- Raj, R., Kumar, M., Ranjan, R., Bharti, P., Sonal, A., & Raipat, B. S. (2025). Ecosystem services provided by dragonflies: Jharkhand context. *Vat-Vriksha*, *2*(1), OM05. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18125864>
- Osga, J., Kumar, M., Mahto, D., Minz, P. A., Herenj, S., Kunkal, R. L., Mahto, S., Khan, M., Pratap, R., Ranjan, R., & Raipat, B. S. (2025). Butterflies from St. Xavier's College (Ranchi) campus: A checklist. *Vat-Vriksha*, *1*(1), OM06. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16572855>
- Kumar, M., Ranjan, R., Kumar, A., Pratik, R., Hembrom, R., & Tirkey, S. (2025e). Current studies on butterfly conservation in Jharkhand: A data-oriented analysis. *Vat-Vriksha*, *1*(1), OM03. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15834007>
- Choudhary, J. S., Singh, R., & Sharma, P. (2015). Biology and pest status of hemipteran insects in India. *Indian Journal of Entomology*, *77*(2), 123–130.
- Singh, R., & Singh, G. (2021). Faunal diversity of spiders (Chelicerata: Araneae) in Bihar and Jharkhand, India. *International Journal of Biological Innovations*, *3*(2), 382–391. <https://doi.org/10.46505/IJBI.2021.3220>
- Hebert, P. D. N., Cywinska, A., Ball, S. L., & deWaard, J. R. (2003). Biological identifications through DNA barcodes. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *270*(1512), 313–321. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2002.2218>
- Srivastava, R., Kumar, M., Ranjan, R., Dandapat, S., & Sinha, M. P. (2024). Morpho-molecular taxonomy and bioinformatics-based phylogeny of *Metaphire posthuma*. *The Bioscan*, *19*(1), 45–52.
- Kumar, M., Ranjan, R., & Sinha, M. P. (2022). A review on insect collection and preservation techniques. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, *9*(7), 233–239.
- Parveen, S., Choudhary, J. S., & Thomas, A. (2015). Biology, morphology and DNA barcodes of *Tessaratomia javanica* (Hemiptera: Tessaratomidae). *Zootaxa*, *3946*(3), 351–365. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3946.3.3>
- Schuh, R. T., & Slater, J. A. (1995). *True bugs of the world (Hemiptera: Heteroptera): Classification and natural history*. Cornell University Press.
- Triplehorn, C. A., & Johnson, N. F. (2005). *Borror and DeLong's introduction to the study of insects* (7th ed.). Thomson Brooks/Cole.
- Ahmad, I., & Kamaluddin, S. (1981). A revision of Tessaratomidae (Hemiptera: Pentatomoidea) from the Indo-Pakistan subcontinent. *Oriental Insects*, *15*(1), 1–70. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00305316.1981.10434332>
- Saitou, N., & Nei, M. (1987). The neighbor-joining method: A new method for reconstructing phylogenetic trees. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, *4*(4), 406–425. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.molbev.a040454>
- Tamura, K., Nei, M., & Kumar, S. (2004). Prospects for inferring very large phylogenies using the neighbor-joining method. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *101*(30), 11030–11035. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0404206101>
- Hebert, P. D. N., Ratnasingham, S., & deWaard, J. R. (2004). Barcoding animal life: COI divergences among closely related species. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B*, *270*(Suppl. 1), S96–S99. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2003.0025>
- Panizzi, A. R., McPherson, J. E., James, D. G., Javahery, M., & McPherson, R. M. (2000). Stink bugs (Pentatomidae). In C. W. Schaefer & A. R. Panizzi (Eds.), *Heteroptera of economic importance* (pp. 421–474). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781420041859>
- Rao, S. L., & Ramesh, K. (2013). Biology and management of *Tessaratomia javanica*, a major pest of litchi. *Journal of Biological Control*, *27*(2), 129–134.
- Wang, Y., & Bu, W. (2012). Phylogeny of Pentatomidae based on mitochondrial and nuclear gene sequences. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, *62*(2), 400–415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2011.10.012>
- Distant, W. L. (1902). *The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma: Rhynchota* (Vol. 1). Taylor & Francis.
- Zhang, J., & Lin, S. (2015). Taxonomic review of the genus *Tessaratomia*. *Zootaxa*, *3955*(1), 1–45. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3955.1.1>
- Thunberg, C. P. (1783). *Dissertationes entomologicae*. Uppsala University.

27. Drury, D. (1773). *Illustrations of natural history* (Vol. 2). London.
28. Fabricius, J. C. (1787). *Mantissa insectorum* (Vol. 2). Hafniae.
29. Westwood, J. O. (1837). *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London*. Zoological Society of London.
30. Henry, T. J. (1997). Phylogenetic analysis of Pentatomomorpha family groups. *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*, 90(3), 275–301. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aesa/90.3.275>
31. Rider, D. A., Schwertner, C. F., Vilímová, J., & Rédei, D. (2018). Higher systematics of Pentatomoidea. *Zootaxa*, 4369(1), 1–162. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4369.1.1>
32. Gross, G. F. (1975). Revision of Australian and Indo-Pacific Tessaratomidae. *Records of the South Australian Museum*, 17, 275–308.
33. Hua, L. (2000). *List of Chinese insects*. Zhongshan University Press.
34. EPPO. (2023). *Tessaratomia javanica: Distribution and pest status*. EPPO Global Database. <https://gd.eppo.int>
35. Tamura, K., Stecher, G., & Kumar, S. (2021). MEGA11: Molecular evolutionary genetics analysis version 11. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 38(7), 3022–3027. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msab120>
36. Nei, M., & Kumar, S. (2000). *Molecular evolution and phylogenetics*. Oxford University Press.
37. Wright, S. (1943). Isolation by distance. *Genetics*, 28(2), 114–138. <https://doi.org/10.1093/genetics/28.2.114>
38. Slatkin, M. (1993). Isolation by distance in equilibrium and non-equilibrium populations. *Evolution*, 47(1), 264–279. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1558-5646.1993.tb01215.x>
39. Samal, I., Choudhary, J. S., & Raj, A. (2025). Dynamics of bacterial communities across developmental stages of *Tessaratomia javanica*. *Scientific Reports*, 15, Article 29106. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-22985-1>

आकृतिक विशेषताओं तथा COI जीन बारकोडिंग के आधार पर भारत के झारखंड से प्राप्त लीची स्टिंक बग (*Tessaratomia javanica*) का समन्वित वर्गिकी अध्ययन

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सारांश

भारत के झारखंड राज्य के 10 विभिन्न स्थलों से संकलित नमूनों के आधार पर लीची स्टिंक बग *Tessaratomia javanica* (Hemiptera: Tessaratomidae) का समेकित वर्गिकी अध्ययन आकृतिक लक्षणों एवं माइटोकॉण्ड्रियल साइटोक्रोम c ऑक्सीडेज उपएकाई-1 (COI) जीन बारकोडिंग द्वारा किया गया। सभी वयस्क नमूनों में बड़ा ढालाकार शरीर, विस्तारित प्रोनोटम, त्रिकोणीय स्क्यूटेलम, पंच-खंडीय स्पर्शक तथा सुदृढ़ रोस्ट्रम जैसी समान नैदानिक विशेषताएँ पाई गईं, जो आकृतिक एकरूपता को दर्शाती हैं। प्रतिनिधि नमूनों से 612–690 bp लंबाई वाले COI जीन खंडों का सफलतापूर्वक प्रवर्धन एवं अनुक्रमण किया गया। BLASTn विश्लेषण ने सभी अनुक्रमों की पहचान *T. javanica* के रूप में पुष्टि की। इस सत्यापित COI अनुक्रम DDBJ डेटाबेस में अभिगमन संख्या LC911186–LC911195 के अंतर्गत जमा किए गए। न्यूक्लियोटाइड संरचना में स्पष्ट AT-पक्षपात पाया गया। आनुवंशिक दूरी विश्लेषण से अत्यंत निम्न अंतःप्रजातीय विचलन तथा उच्च आनुवंशिक समरूपता का संकेत मिला। अधिकतम संभाव्यता, निकटतम-संयोजन एवं न्यूनतम उत्क्रांति विधियों पर आधारित वंशवृक्षीय विश्लेषणों में सभी नमूने एक सुदृढ़ एकवंशी क्लेड में समूहित हुए। परिणाम *T. javanica* की वर्गिकीय स्थिरता की पुष्टि करते हैं तथा कीट निदान, जैवविविधता अभिलेखीकरण एवं भावी जनसंख्या आनुवंशिकी अध्ययनों हेतु आधारभूत संदर्भ प्रदान करते हैं।

कुंजी: आकृति-आणविक सामंजस्य; अंतःप्रजातीय विविधता; COI जीन बारकोडिंग; आनुवंशिक समरूपता; कीट निदान।

1. Ranchi
LC911186

2. Latehar
LC911187

3. Palamu
LC911188

4. Garhwa
LC911189

5. Hazaribagh
LC911190

6. Bokaro
LC911191

7. Giridih
LC911192

8. Dhanbad
LC911193

9. Jamshedpur
LC911194

10. Godda
LC911195

Figure 1: Tessaratoma javanica physical specimens representing their respective collection sites and corresponding Accession IDS

Figure 2: Map of Jharkhand State of India, showing different survey locations for sampling of *Tassarotoma javanica* specimens from 10 different locations (1: Ormanjhi (Ranchi); 2: Latehar Forest Edge, 3: Daltonganj, Palamu; 4: Garhwa; 5: Hazaribagh; 6: Bokaro; 7: Giridih; 8: Dhanbad; 9: Jamshedpur, 10: Godda) – Map created with the help of Google Maps and Google Earth Pro

Forewings

Hindwings

Figure 3: Forewings and Hindwings of Tessaratoma javanica

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
LC911186.1_Tj_Ranchi	1		0.00647	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.07053	0.00647	0.00647
LC911187.1_Tj_Latehar	2	0.00647		0.00647	0.00647	0.00647	0.00647	0.00647	0.06888	0.00000	0.00000
LC911188.1_Tj_Palamu	3	0.00000	0.00647		0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.07053	0.00647	0.00647
LC911189.1_Tj_Garhwa	4	0.00000	0.00647	0.00000		0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.07053	0.00647	0.00647
LC911190.1_Tj_Hazaribagh	5	0.00000	0.00647	0.00000	0.00000		0.00000	0.00000	0.07053	0.00647	0.00647
LC911191.1_Tj_Bokaro	6	0.00000	0.00647	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000		0.00000	0.07053	0.00647	0.00647
LC911192.1_Tj_Giridih	7	0.00000	0.00647	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000		0.07053	0.00647	0.00647
LC911193.1_Tj_Dhanbad	8	0.07053	0.06888	0.07053	0.07053	0.07053	0.07053	0.07053		0.06888	0.06888
LC911194.1_Tj_Jamshedpur	9	0.00647	0.00000	0.00647	0.00647	0.00647	0.00647	0.00647	0.06888		0.00000
LC911195.1_Tj_Godda	10	0.00647	0.00000	0.00647	0.00647	0.00647	0.00647	0.00647	0.06888	0.00000	

Figure 4: Distance matrix showing genetic distance between the 10 COI sequences of *Tessaratomia javanica*

Figure 5: Evolutionary analysis by Maximum Likelihood Method

Figure 6: Evolutionary analysis by Neighbour-Joining Method

Figure 7: Evolutionary analysis using Minimum Evolution Method

Table 1: Sampling locations of *Tessaratomia javanica* across Jharkhand, India (2025).

Site No.	Location	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°E)	Date (2025)	Time	Habitat Type
1	Ranchi (Ormanjhi)	23.3942	85.3841	18 Mar	08:00-10:00	Litchi orchard
2	Latehar Forest Edge	23.7461	84.5369	22 Mar	15:30-17:30	Forest-orchard ecotone
3	Palamu (Daltonganj)	24.0415	84.0652	26 Mar	07:30-09:30	Rural agro-forest
4	Garhwa	24.1628	83.8076	30 Mar	08:00-10:00	Mixed cultivation
5	Hazaribagh	23.9964	85.3692	04 Apr	15:00-17:00	Orchard belt
6	Bokaro	23.7873	85.9564	10 Apr	07:30-09:30	Peri-urban orchard
7	Giridih	24.1825	86.3036	15 Apr	08:00-10:00	Agricultural mosaic
8	Dhanbad	23.7951	86.4302	20 Apr	15:30-17:30	Rural-urban fringe
9	Jamshedpur	22.8049	86.2027	28 Apr	08:00-10:00	Orchard-forest edge
10	Godda	24.8256	87.2189	05 May	15:00-17:00	Eastern plateau orchards

Table 2: Collection sites and voucher numbers of *Tessarotoma javanica* specimens from Jharkhand, India (2025)

Sl. No.	Collection Site (Jharkhand)	Voucher Number	Accession ID
1	Ranchi (Ormanjhi)	SXCRAN-ENT-TJ-2025-01	LC911186
2	Latehar (Forest Edge)	SXCRAN-ENT-TJ-2025-02	LC911187
3	Palamu (Daltonganj)	SXCRAN-ENT-TJ-2025-03	LC911188
4	Garhwa	SXCRAN-ENT-TJ-2025-04	LC911189
5	Hazaribagh	SXCRAN-ENT-TJ-2025-05	LC911190
6	Bokaro	SXCRAN-ENT-TJ-2025-06	LC911191
7	Giridih	SXCRAN-ENT-TJ-2025-07	LC911192
8	Dhanbad	SXCRAN-ENT-TJ-2025-08	LC911193
9	Jamshedpur (East Singhbhum)	SXCRAN-ENT-TJ-2025-09	LC911194
10	Godda	SXCRAN-ENT-TJ-2025-10	LC911195

Table 3: Physical Distance Matrix (km) between Sampling Sites of *Tessarotoma javanica*

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Ranchi	1	0	94.8	152.3	181.8	67	72.9	128.2	115.5	106.3	245
Latehar	2	94.8	0	58.1	87.4	89.1	144.5	186	192.7	199.8	297.1
Palamu	3	152.3	58.1	0	29.4	132.5	194.3	227.7	241.9	257.8	330.9
Garhwa	4	181.8	87.4	29.4	0	159.6	222.3	253.2	269.6	287.2	353
Hazaribagh	5	67	89.1	132.5	159.6	0	64.1	97.1	110.2	157.4	208.8
Bokaro	6	72.9	144.5	194.3	222.3	64.1	0	56.3	48.2	112.1	172.3
Giridih	7	128.2	186	227.7	253.2	97.1	56.3	0	45	153.5	117
Dhanbad	8	115.5	192.7	241.9	269.6	110.2	48.2	45	0	112.5	139.7
Jamshedpur	9	106.3	199.8	257.8	287.2	157.4	112.1	153.5	112.5	0	247.3
Godda	10	245	297.1	330.9	353	208.8	172.3	117	139.7	247.3	0

Table 4: Nucleotide Frequencies of *Tessarotoma javanica* Sequences

Accession ID	Sample Name	T(U) (%)	C (%)	A (%)	G (%)	Total Sites
LC911186.1	Tj Ranchi	32.7	17.7	33.0	16.6	651
LC911187.1	Tj Latehar	33.9	17.4	33.0	15.7	690
LC911188.1	Tj Palamu	32.7	17.7	33.0	16.6	651
LC911189.1	Tj Garhwa	32.7	17.7	33.0	16.6	651
LC911190.1	Tj Hazaribagh	32.7	17.7	33.0	16.6	651
LC911191.1	Tj Bokaro	32.7	17.7	33.0	16.6	651
LC911192.1	Tj Giridih	32.7	17.7	33.0	16.6	651
LC911193.1	Tj Dhanbad	32.4	17.0	33.3	17.3	612
LC911194.1	Tj Jamshedpur	33.9	17.4	33.0	15.7	690
LC911195.1	Tj Godda	33.9	17.4	33.0	15.7	690
Average	–	33.1	17.5	33.1	16.4	658.8

